

STUDY OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HEALTH EDUCATION BASED YOGA PROGRAMME FOR NATIONAL SERVICE SCHEME (NSS) STUDENTS

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INTRODUCTION:

Yoga is often partially understood as being limited to asanas or poses, and its benefits are only perceived to be at the physical level. However, we fail to realize the immense benefits yoga offers in uniting the body, mind, and breath. When you are in harmony, the journey through life is calmer, happier and more fulfilling. So, if you are keen to lose weight, develop a strong and flexible body or being at peace, then yoga can help you achieve it all. Yoga will increase your humidity power and you will feel more and more enthusiastic.

The sole aim of the NSS is to provide hands on experience to young students in delivering community service. NSS is voluntary the process of all round development of the students . it is necessary that they should be healthy. Health Education includes physical education, yoga and pranayama, emotional and intellectual .

NEED OF THE STUDY:

1. teachers should inculcate good habits related to health, NSS students are getting health related information and they implement it in their day today life.
2. Yoga is most important for everyone's life as it helps in balancing the relationship between body and mind. It is type of exercise which helps in learning physical and mental discipline through regular practice.
3. To develop mental, spiritual and physical path of NSS students it is much needy to implement Health Education Related yoga Programme for NSS Students.
4. Researcher motivated to undertake research the need to impart health education to NSS students as they are future citizens of India and would be healthier.

TITLE OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM:

Study of the effectiveness of health education based yoga programme for national service scheme (NSS) students

OPERATIONAL DEFENITIONS:

Effectiveness: Significant difference between pre-test and post-test on health education based yoga programme and qualitative feedback from (NSS) students.

Yoga Programme: A plan of action chalked out to impart health education

Health Education: A teaching learning process is developed in order to enhance Physical, mental, Spiritual, and social health of (NSS) students.

NSS students: Students studying in B.Ed College having NSS volunteer in PVDT College of Education For Women, Mumbai.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. to develop health education based yoga programme for national service scheme (NSS) students
2. to study the effectiveness of health education based yoga programme for national service scheme (NSS) students

Hypothesis:

There is significant difference between the mean scores of NSS Students Pre-test and post-test Score about the of health education based yoga programme test.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of NSS Students Pre-test and post-test Score about the of health education based yoga programme test.

Scope and Limitations:**Scope**

1. This research would be conducted on PVDT College of Education For Women, Mumbai
2. This research work will be held with 124 NSS students studying in B.Ed.
3. This research work will be conducted for health education based yoga programme in Academic Year 2019 only

Limitations

1. This research work is limited to PVDT College of Education For Women, Mumbai
2. This research work is limited to 124 NSS students studying in B.Ed.
3. This research work is limited for the health education based yoga programme in Academic Year 2019 only

Significance of the study

1. This study is helpful to check yoga impact on NSS Students.
2. This study is helpful to understand importance of yoga for better Health.
3. This study is helpful to develop mental, spiritual and physical path of NSS students.
4. This study is helpful to helps in balancing the relationship between body and mind.

Design of the study:**Methodology:**

For finding out the effectiveness of health education based yoga programme, an experimental method was used.

Population, sample and sampling method

Population was B.Ed. Students and B.Ed. Colleges affiliated to SNDT Women's University, Mumbai. From the population, PVDT College of Education For Women was selected as college sample by convenience sampling and 124 B.Ed. Student Teacher as sample by random sampling.

Data collection and analysis tools

Data was obtained from samples by students teacher made pre-test and post-test and obtained data was analysed by statistical tools viz., Mean, SD, t-test and effect size.

Tools:

1. Health education based yoga programme Pre Test and Post Test
2. Health education based yoga programme

PROCEDURE:**Preparations for the programme:**

Researcher read reference literature related with Health Education and Yoga. In consultation/discussion with the guide, NSS Program officers, Yoga guide, doctors and colleagues, the research problem was finalized. The programme proposed was prepared.

Conducting Pre-test: All the NSS students of B.Ed. 1st and 2nd Year were given pre-test.

Procedure: The following flowchart depicts the procedure followed for research

Conducting Post-test:

All the NSS students of B.Ed. 1st and 2nd Year were given pre-test after implementation of Health Education Based Yoga Programme.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

After the data was collected, it was processed and analyzed using, SPSS software to draw exact conclusions. To fulfill all the objectives and to test the hypotheses framed, the data collected was subjected statistical analyses namely mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ test.

Testing Hypothesis:

The following text presents the verification of hypothesis using appropriate statistical procedures.

Ho1:

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Student Teacher Pre-test and post-test Score about the social media security awareness program (SMSA) test.

‘t’ test was done to find out the significance of the difference between mean of the pre-test score of the participants .the following table presents the result of the analysis.

Table No: Significance different of the Mean of health education based yoga programme Pre Test and Post Test Score

Test	N	Mean	SD	T Test Score	Los
Pre Test	124	29.25	7.31	2.77	Significance 0.01
Post Test	124	31.75	7.96		

From The above table, it could be seen that the obtained Value of t is 2.77 which is greater then table value of 1.68 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.01 level.

SIGNIFICANCE DIFFERENT OF THE MEAN OF HEALTH EDUCATION BASED YOGA PROGRAMME PRE TEST AND POST TEST SCORE

Conclusion: health education based yoga programme is Effective.

Reference:

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